

A Tracer Study on the Bachelor of Elementary Education Graduates of St. Paul University Surigao A.Y. 2017-2022

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ABSTRACT: A Tracer study is a research method that tracks and collects data on the outcomes and experiences of graduates to assess the effectiveness of educational programs. This research study titled "A Tracer Study on the Bachelor of Elementary Education Graduates of St. Paul University Surigao A.Y. 2017-2022" aimed to trace the employability of graduates and assess their rating of the effectiveness of the teacher education program outcomes. The researchers collected data from 45 graduates using an adapted-modified questionnaire and analyzed using various statistical tools. The findings showed that most of the graduates were female and within the age range of 21-24. Most participants were single, held a bachelor's degree as their highest educational attainment, and graduated in 2018. The Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) was taken by 31 graduates, with professional education subjects identified as the most challenging area. Six months after graduation, at least 62% of the graduates who responded remained unemployed, while those employed mostly worked as grade school teachers. The competencies learned during college, such as communication, information technology skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving, were reported as valuable in their first jobs. Graduates highlighted the development of attributes such as communication and relational skills, academic excellence, critical thinking, research, problem-solving, leadership, teamwork, social and ethical responsibility, productivity, and accountability during their undergraduate studies. Graduates rated the nine teacher education program outcomes as very effective. The study's conclusion recommends targeted support for licensure exam preparation, enhancing employability and job placement, and bridging the education-employment gap.

KEYWORDS: Employability, Tracer study, Teacher education program outcomes, St. Paul University Surigao, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

The demand for expanded access to high-quality tertiary education is growing as the number of young people keeps increasing and elementary and secondary school graduation rates soar. To equip students with knowledge and skills applicable to the job market, tertiary technical and vocational education and training may serve as an effective and efficient complement to regular university study. [1]

A way to keep the curriculum current and give graduates specific benefits to increase the marketability of educational programs is through tracer studies or graduate surveys. The formulation of policy to address some societal issues, such as unemployment, could be aided by an adequate understanding of the employment outcomes of training graduates. Students, in particular graduates of any course, must gain a sense of competence in their area of interest and build the confidence to explore other opportunities and new employment, particularly if there is growing rivalry among coworkers. [2]

St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS) has subsequently performed and submitted a tracer study to the Caraga Region's CHED Zonal Research Center (ZRC). It is then that the researcher saw the need to conduct its very own tracer study and establish the relevancy of its program as well as its employability index of its graduates, especially since it is applying for PAASCU Accreditation and the data gathered will be of pivotal importance as evidence of sound curricular and instructional offerings. [3]

Conducting tracer studies in universities is crucial for evaluating academic programs, assessing graduates' employability, maintaining alumni relationships, and ensuring overall accountability. By tracking graduates' career paths and outcomes, universities can identify areas for improvement, align programs with job market demands, and enhance students' skills to meet

industry needs. Tracer studies provide valuable feedback on graduates' readiness for employment, enabling universities to continuously strengthen the quality of education and prepare students for successful careers.

The researcher's objective was to trace the demographic profile of the graduates, identify competencies that were useful to the graduates in their first job, examine the attributes learned during undergraduate studies, assess the effectiveness of the Teacher Education Program Outcomes (POs), and the significant relationships among different personal profile variables and the employability of the respondents in order to propose an enhanced development plan.

RESEARCH PROBLEMS

This study aimed to trace the employability of Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates of St. Paul University Surigao A.Y. 2017 to 2022. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents with regards to:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 civil stats;
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5 year graduated;
 - 1.6 professional examination/s passed;
 - 1.7 number of trainings attended after college relevant to the field;
 - 1.8 most difficult area during the licensure examination;
 - 1.9 employment status; and
 - 1.10. present occupation?
2. What competencies were learned in college useful to the first job?
3. What attributes were learned during undergraduate studies?
4. What is the extent of effectiveness of the Teacher Education Program Outcomes (POs)?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what recommendations can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative research design using a descriptive-survey method to determine the employability of St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS) graduates with Bachelor of Elementary Education AY 2017-2022 degrees. The researchers chose the survey technique as it was deemed the most suitable approach to gather data on the graduates' demographic profile, competencies learned in college that applied to their first job, attributes acquired during their undergraduate studies, the extent of effectiveness of the Teacher Education Program Outcomes (POs), and proposed recommendation to enhance board performance and employability of the Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates.

The study focused on St. Paul University Surigao (SPUS) graduates with a Bachelor of Elementary Education from A.Y. 2017-2022. Out of 87 graduates from the BEED program at St. Paul University Surigao between 2017 and 2022, the researchers successfully gathered 45 participants, which accounted for 52% of the total population. Convenience sampling was used as a sampling technique to gather data for evaluation. It meant that the researchers collected data from those conveniently available to participate in the study. Questionnaires were provided through Google Forms to the participants to ascertain the employability status of the graduates.

The study used a modified-adapted questionnaire as a significant tool for gathering data and was presented to the experts to validate the content. The sources of the modified-adapted questionnaire were adapted from the Commission on Higher Education Tracer Study and Professional Qualifications and Tracer Instrument from Professional Qualifications, Academic Competencies of Teachers, and Employability of Graduates. The survey questionnaire comprises five main components: demographic profile; competencies that were useful to the graduates' first job; attributes learned during undergraduate studies; effectiveness of Teacher Education's Program Outcomes (POs); and different personal profile variables and employability of the graduates. It aimed to measure the employability of BEED graduates by assessing various factors related to their education and employment. [4] [5]

The data gathered were organized, tallied, and analyzed using Microsoft Excel and IBM SPSS Statistics Version 22. Specifically, it utilized the following statistical tools for the analysis of data:

Frequency Count and Percentage. These tools were used to describe the profile variables of the respondents in terms of sex, age, civil status, highest educational attainment, degree of specialization, year graduated, professional examination(s) passed, and number of trainings attended after college relevant to the field.

Mean and Standard Deviation. These tools were used to describe and interpret the effectiveness of the teacher education program outcomes. Mean is a sufficient statistic to describe and interpret Likert-scale data. [6]

Mann Whitney U-Test. This tool is a non-parametric test used to determine if significant difference exists in the level of effectiveness of the teacher education program outcomes when the respondents are grouped based on sex, civil status, and highest educational attainment. The median was used with Z-value as the test statistic in this test. Further, the normality of the data was first checked and analyzed using Shapiro-Wilk Test. Some data were not normally distributed which led the researcher to use this non-parametric test.

Kruskal Wallis H-Test. This tool is a non-parametric test used to determine if significant difference exists in the level of effectiveness of the teacher education program outcomes when the respondents are grouped based on age, degree of specialization, year graduated, and professional examination(s) passed. The median was used with Chi-square value as the test statistic in this test. Further, the normality of the data was first checked and analyzed using Shapiro-Wilk Test. Some data were found to be not normally distributed leading the researcher to use this non-parametric test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1.7 Profile of the Respondents

GROUP		f (n=45)	%
Age	21-24	27	60
	25-28	16	35.56
	29 years old and above	2	4.44
Sex	Male	5	11.11
	Female	40	88.89
Civil Status	Single	41	91.11
	Married	3	6.67
	Single Parent	1	2.22
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	42	93.33
	Master's Degree	3	6.67
Year Graduated	2017	7	15.56
	2018	11	24.44
	2019	8	17.78
	2020	1	2.22
	2021	8	17.78
	2022	10	22.22
Professional Examination(s) Passed	Board Licensure Examination for Professional Teachers	24	53.51

Civil Service	2	4.44
None	19	42.22

No. of Trainings Attended After College Relevant to the Field

None	15	33.33
1 to 5	16	35.55
6 to 15	5	11.11
16 to 30	7	15.55
More than 30	2	4.44

As shown in Table 1, in terms of age, majority of the respondents 27 or 60% fall between the ages of 21 – 24 years old. Then followed by 25-28 years old with 16 or 36%; and 29 years old above with 2 or 4% respondents. Regarding sex, 40 or 90% of the participants were female, and 5 or 11% were male out of 45 participants. Regarding to the civil status, 41 or 91% of the respondents are single, while 3 or 7% are married, and 1 or 2% is single parent across all batches. As to the highest educational attainment of the participants, majority of the respondents with 42 or 93% has Bachelor’s Degree and 3 or 7% have Master’s Degree. Meanwhile, as to the year they graduated, 11 or 24% of the respondents belonged to 2018. Then followed 2022 with 10 or 22%; 2021 and 2019 with 8 or 18%; 2017 with 7 or 16%; and 2020 with 1 or 2%. Regarding the professional examination passed, majority of the respondents passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) with 24 or 54%, then 19 or 42% answered none, and only 2 or 4% for Civil Service Examination. As to the number of trainings attended after college relevant to the field, the responses from 45 participants were as follows: 16 respondents or 36% attended 1 to 5 trainings; 15 or 33% did not have any training experienced; 7 or 16% attended 16 to 30 trainings; 5 or 11% attended 6 to 15 trainings; and 2 or 4% attended more than 30 trainings.

Table 1.8. Most Difficult Area during Licensure Examination

AREA	f (n=45)	%	Rank
General Education Subjects	12	26.67	2 ND
Professional Education Subjects	19	42.22	1 ST
Did not take the exam	14	31.11	

With regards to the most difficult area during the licensure examination, general education subjects were rated as the second most difficult, with 12 respondents or 27%. Professional education subjects were rated as the most difficult by 19 respondents or 42%. Additionally, out of the 45 respondents, 31% did not take the licensure examination.

Table 1.9. Employment Status within Six Months After Graduation

STATUS	f(n=45)	%	Rank
Unemployed	28	62.22	1 ST
Employed	17	37.78	2 ND

Regarding employment status within six months after graduation, majority of the respondents, with 28 or 62%, were unemployed, ranking it first, and 17 or 38% were employed, placing it in the second rank.

Table 1.10. Present Occupation Status

OCCUPATION	FREQUENCY	RANK
Grade School Teacher	24	1 ST
Call Center Agent	2	2 ND
Government Employee	2	2 ND
Private Tutor	2	2 ND
Senior High School Teacher	1	3 RD
CDS Office Secretary	1	3 RD
Small Business	1	3 RD
Online Seller	1	3 RD
Self-employed	1	3 RD
Firefighter	1	3 RD
Billing Clerk	1	3 RD
Volunteer	1	3 RD
Administrative Assistance	1	3 RD

In terms of the present occupation status of the graduates, it can be gleaned that the participants are currently working as grade school teachers, with 24 respondents ranking it first; 5 respondents having no work; followed by call-center agents, government employees, and private tutors with 2 respondents each, on second rank; followed by senior high school teacher, firefighter, CDS office secretary, small business, online seller, self-employed, billing clerk, and volunteer with the same number of 1 respondents each, placing it on the third rank.

Table 2. Competencies learned in college that were useful in your first job

COMPETENCIES	FREQUENCY	Rank
Communication Skills	42	1 ST
Information Technology Skills	32	2 ND
Critical Thinking Skills	32	2 ND
Problem-solving Skills	31	3 RD
Human Relation Skills	29	4 TH
Entrepreneurial Skills	11	5 TH
Others (Innovative Skills)	1	6 TH

Regarding the competencies learned in college that were useful in respondents' first jobs, communication skills were the most useful competency, with 42 respondents ranking it in the first rank. Information technology skills and critical thinking skills were both ranked second, each with a frequency of 32; problem-solving skills closely followed in the third rank, with 31 respondents; human relation skills were recognized as useful by 29 respondents, ranking them in the fourth rank. Entrepreneurial skills were recognized by 11 respondents, placing them in the fifth rank. Lastly, innovative skills had the lowest frequency, being mentioned only once, indicating their limited recognition among the respondents.

The competencies learned in college, including undergraduate specialization, skills, and knowledge, significantly contribute to graduates' productivity, efficiency, and expertise in their present jobs. This aligns with the interpreted data, where communication skills were ranked as the most useful competency, followed by information technology and critical thinking skills. Problem-solving skills, human relation skills, and entrepreneurial skills were also recognized as important. However, innovative skills had limited recognition among respondents, indicating the need for increased emphasis on their importance. The tracer study on the graduates of Medan State University further supports these findings, highlighting the relevance of these competencies for successful workforce transition, short waiting periods for employment, and high satisfaction among employers. Overall, these studies emphasize the importance of these competencies in enhancing graduates' employability and success in their careers. [7]

Table 3. Attributes learned during undergraduate studies

ATTRIBUTES	FREQUENCY	Rank
Communication and Relational Skills	38	1 ST
Academic Excellence	35	2 ND
Critical Thinking, Research and Problem-Solving Skills	34	3 RD
Leadership and Teamwork	32	4 TH
Social and Ethical Responsibility	32	4 TH
Productivity and Accountability	29	5 TH

In terms of the attributes learned during undergraduate studies, Communication and Relational Skills, with 38 respondents, were ranked first; Academic Excellence followed closely behind in the second rank, with 35 respondents; Critical Thinking, Research, and Problem-Solving Skills ranked third, with 34 respondents; Leadership and Teamwork" and "Social and Ethical Responsibility" tied for the fourth rank, each mentioned by 32 respondents; and Productivity and Accountability with 29 respondents, placing it in the fifth rank.

Employability encompasses achievements, including skills, understandings, and personal attributes that enhance individuals' likelihood of gaining employment and succeeding in their chosen careers. This not only benefits the individuals themselves but also has positive implications for the workforce, the community, and the economy as a whole. The data presented on attributes learned during undergraduate studies supports and aligns with these concepts. Communication and Relational Skills were ranked first, indicating the importance of strong interpersonal abilities for career success. Academic Excellence closely followed, emphasizing the significance of a solid academic foundation. Critical Thinking, Research, and Problem-Solving Skills ranked third, highlighting the ability to tackle complex challenges. Leadership and Teamwork, along with Social and Ethical Responsibility, tied for the fourth rank, reflecting the value of collaboration and ethical behavior. Finally, Productivity and Accountability ranked fifth, underscoring the importance of a strong work ethic and a sense of responsibility. These attributes collectively contribute to graduates' employability, enhancing their prospects in their chosen careers and positively impacting the workforce and society. [8]

Table 4. Effectiveness of Teacher Education’s Program Outcomes

Program Outcomes (Pos)	M	SD	VI	QD
1.Knowledge in the Teaching Field - Articulate the rootedness of education in philosophical, sociocultural, historical, psychological, and political contexts	3.53	0.50	A	VE
2.Socially Collaborative - Develop innovative curricula, instructional plans, teaching approaches, and resources for diverse learner	3.56	0.50	A	VE
3.Pedagogically Competent - Facilitate learning using a teaching methodologies and delivery modes appropriate to the learners and their environment	3.56	0.50	A	VE
4.Technically Competent - Utilize appropriate assessment and evaluation tools to measure learning outcomes	3.47	0.59	A	VE
5.Effective Communicator - Manifest skills in communication, higher order thinking and use of tools and technology to accelerate learning and teaching	3.56	0.50	A	VE
6.Technically Competent - Apply skills in the development and utilization of ICT to promote quality, relevant, and sustainable educational practices	3.62	0.49	A	VE
7. Globally Competent - Practice professional and ethical teaching standards sensitive to the local, national and global realities	3.49	0.55	A	VE
8. Ethically Responsible - Display positive attributes of a model teacher, both as an individual and as a professional	3.64	0.49	A	VE

9. Lifelong Learner - Pursue lifelong learning for personal and professional growth through varied experiential and field-based opportunities

	3.67	0.48	A	VE
AVERAGE	3.57	0.51	A	VE

Legend:

Parameter	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
3.25 - 4.00	Always	Very Effective
2.50 - 3.24	Often	Moderately Effective
1.75 - 2.49	Sometimes	Slightly Effective
1.00 - 1.74	Rarely	Not Effective

Table 4 presented the effectiveness of the teacher education program outcomes. It has the average mean of 3.57 and standard deviation of 0.51 and is described qualitatively as very effective. It indicated that the graduates perceived the outcomes to have been highly successful in meeting the intended goals and objectives of the program. They acknowledged that the program had effectively equipped them with the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies required for their future roles as teachers.

Teacher Education Program Outcomes by CHED memorandum order no. 75 series of 2017 presents the programs as follows: Firstly, education is deeply rooted in philosophical, socio-cultural, historical, psychological, and political contexts, requiring an understanding of these foundations. Secondly, teachers should display mastery in their respective subject areas or disciplines. Thirdly, they should employ a diverse range of teaching methodologies and delivery modes that suit specific learners and their environments. Fourthly, they should create innovative curricula, instructional plans, teaching approaches, and resources tailored to different types of learners. Fifthly, they should possess skills in utilizing ICT to enhance educational practices that are of high quality, relevant, and sustainable. Sixthly, they should demonstrate critical thinking skills in various aspects of education, such as planning, monitoring, assessing, and reporting learning processes and outcomes. Seventhly, teachers should adhere to professional and ethical standards that consider local, national, and global realities. Lastly, they should embrace lifelong learning for personal and professional growth by actively engaging in varied experiential and field-based opportunities. [9]

The effectiveness of the teacher education program outcomes is given the average mean of 3.57 and SD of 0.51 qualitatively described as very effective. In terms of teacher education’s program outcomes, the highest-rated item is lifelong learner - pursue lifelong learning for personal and professional growth through varied experiential and field-based opportunities, which obtained 3.67 and a standard deviation of 0.48 described as very effective. This implies that the participants have grown personally and professionally and applied these in teaching or in any field of endeavor. Key attributes that a teacher who embodies lifelong learning should possess several important qualities. Firstly, they should have self-awareness, indicating a deep understanding of their own strengths, weaknesses, and personal growth areas. Secondly, they should possess professional skills, demonstrating competence in their subject areas and a wide range of teaching, planning, evaluation, and interaction skills. Additionally, they should exhibit flexibility, being open to self-renewal and adaptable to changing circumstances. Moreover, they should have strong teamwork skills, being prepared to collaborate and contribute as a valuable team player. Lastly, they should demonstrate empathy and compassion, showing understanding and the ability to engage effectively with students who may feel alienated or have learning difficulties. [10]

The lowest rated item is technically competent - utilize appropriate assessment and evaluation tools to measure learning outcomes, obtained a mean of 3.47 and a standard deviation of 0.59. Despite being the lowest rated, it is still described as very effective qualitatively. This implies that the participants have gained and applied skills in the use of technology in teaching. A teacher who possesses technical competence should demonstrate several abilities. These include being proficient in operating computers and utilizing basic software for tasks like word processing, spreadsheets, and email. They should also be capable of evaluating and effectively using computers and other ICT tools for instructional purposes. Furthermore, they should be able to apply current instructional principles, research, and appropriate assessment practices to incorporate ICTs into their teaching. This entails evaluating educational software, creating engaging computer-based presentations, effectively searching the internet for relevant resources, integrating ICT into student activities across different subjects, producing multimedia content to enhance instruction, demonstrating an understanding of ethical and equitable technology usage, and staying up-to-date with educational technology advancements. [11]

Employability is defined as a collection of achievements, skills, understandings, and personal attributes that enhance individuals' likelihood of gaining employment and succeeding in their chosen careers, benefiting not only the individuals themselves but also the workforce, the community, and the economy as a whole. In line with this concept, the data presented in Table 4 demonstrates the effectiveness of the teacher education program, with an average mean of 3.57 and a standard deviation of 0.51, describing it qualitatively as "very effective." Graduates perceived the outcomes to be highly successful in meeting the intended goals and equipping them with the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies required for their future roles as teachers. This suggests that the program plays a significant role in enhancing graduates' employability and potential success as educators, contributing positively to both individual career prospects and the broader educational landscape. [8]

Table 5. Significant Difference in the Effectiveness of the Teacher Education Program Outcomes

Profile Variables	Z-statistic	Chi-square	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age		1.187	0.553	Do not reject HO	Not Significant
Sex	-1.505		0.132	Do not reject HO	Not Significant
Civil Status		3.183	0.204	Do not reject HO	Not Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-1.850		0.064	Do not reject HO	Not Significant
Year Graduated		4.821	0.438	Do not reject HO	Not Significant
Professional Examination(s) Passed		0.934	0.627	Do not reject HO	Not Significant
No. of Training Attended after College relevant to the Field		1.184	0.881	Do not reject HO	Not Significant

Table 6. Employment Status of the Graduates Per Academic Year

Year Graduated	No. of total graduates	No. of respondents	%	No. of employed	%	No. of unemployed	%	Employability rate
2017	15	7	46.67	7	100	0	0	100%
2018	23	11	47.83	11	100	0	0	100%
2019	15	8	53.33	6	75.00	2	25.00	75%
2020	1	1	100	1	100	0	0	100%
2021	14	8	57.14	7	87.50	1	12.50	87.50%
2022	18	10	55.56	7	70.00	3	30.00	70%

As shown in Table 5, all p-values are greater than the 0.05 significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in the level of effectiveness of the teacher education program outcomes when the respondents were grouped based on profile. All p-values were obtained from statistical tests were found to be greater than the predetermined significance level of 0.05. This implies that the variables considered in the study, such as age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, year graduated, professional examination passed, and number of relevant trainings attended after college, did not have a significant impact on the effectiveness of the teacher education program outcomes. In other words, these factors did not show a statistically significant association with the outcomes of the program. The findings suggest that teacher education

programs should not overly prioritize these demographic or background factors when designing or evaluating the effectiveness of their programs. Instead, other factors or aspects of the program, such as curriculum design, teaching methodologies, mentorship, and practical experiences, may have a more significant impact on program outcomes. It implies that resources and efforts invested in modifying the program specifically to different demographic groups may not yield substantial improvements in overall program effectiveness. Instead, a more standardized approach that focuses on the core components of the program may be sufficient to produce positive outcomes. The teacher education program outcomes are relatively consistent across various demographic and background characteristics. This suggests that the program may be effective in equipping teachers with the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies regardless of their personal characteristics or experiences.

Table 6 presented data on the employment status of graduates from St. Paul University Surigao for the years 2017 to 2022. In 2017, out of 15 graduates, all 7 respondents were employed, resulting in a 100% employability rate. In 2018, out of 23 graduates, all 11 respondents were employed, achieving a 100% employability rate. In 2019, out of 15 graduates, 8 participated, with 6 employed (75%) and 2 unemployed (25%), resulting in a 75% employability rate. In 2020, the 1 graduate was employed, reflecting a 100% employability rate. In 2021, out of 14 graduates, 8 participated, with 7 employed (87.50%) and 1 unemployed (12.50%), leading to an 87.50% employability rate. In 2022, out of 18 graduates, 10 respondents participated, with 7 employed (70%) and 3 unemployed (30%), yielding a 70% employability rate. The data showcasing variations in the employment status of graduates from St. Paul University Surigao over the years 2017 to 2022 aligns with the challenges brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic and changing economic conditions. The study indicates that the pandemic had a significant impact on the job market, leading to fluctuations in employability rates. The overall positive outcomes for most years, despite the fluctuations, highlight the resilience of the surveyed graduates and their adaptability to the evolving circumstances. The study further emphasizes the importance of equipping graduates with relevant knowledge, skills, and values, which aligns with the need for 21st-century skills and socioemotional competencies in the workplace. As the pandemic led to rising unemployment rates, higher education institutions faced pressure to equip students with in-demand skills. The study emphasizes the significance of preparing graduates to navigate industry-specific challenges and individual circumstances, contributing to their employability success during these uncertain times. [12]

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings from the research study on the Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates of St. Paul University Surigao, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The competencies learned by the graduates during their college education were reported as useful in their first jobs. Communication skills were considered the most valuable, followed closely by information technology skills and critical thinking skills. Problem-solving skills, human relations skills, and entrepreneurial skills were also recognized as beneficial by the graduates.
2. Graduates emphasized the significance of communication and relational skills, academic excellence, critical thinking, research, problem-solving skills, leadership and teamwork, social and ethical responsibility, productivity, and accountability as attributes developed during their undergraduate studies.
3. The graduates rated the effectiveness of the teacher education program outcomes highly across all dimensions. The program outcomes related to knowledge in the teaching field, social collaboration, pedagogical competence, technical competence, effective communication, global competence, ethical responsibility, and lifelong learning were all rated as "Always" and described as "Very Effective."

Taking into consideration the findings and conclusions of the study, the researchers have given recommendations:

1. St. Paul University Surigao should continuously review and update the curriculum of the Bachelor of Elementary Education program to ensure it aligns with the evolving needs of the education sector. This can involve incorporating emerging trends in teaching methodologies, integrating technology into the curriculum, and enhancing practical training opportunities for students to strengthen their skills and competencies.
2. Teachers should continue implement practical and hands-on teaching methods that focus on developing the identified competencies, such as communication, information technology, critical thinking, problem-solving, and human relations skills. Offer opportunities for students to engage in real-world projects, collaborative learning, and leadership roles within the school community

to enhance their competence and employability in the teaching profession. Additionally, facilitate workshops and seminars to help students understand the demands of the job market and guide them in effectively showcasing their skills and attributes to potential employers.

3. College of Education Culture and Arts Department should prioritize the continuous development of essential competencies and attributes identified by the graduates. This can be achieved through practical learning experiences, innovative teaching methodologies, and continuous professional development for faculty, ensuring graduates are well-prepared for their teaching careers.

4. Future researchers should conduct the same Tracer Study with larger numbers of participants to enhance the study's reliability, effectiveness, and statistical power. Longitudinal studies tracking graduates' employability beyond six months post-graduation are recommended for a comprehensive understanding of long-term employment outcomes. Measures to enhance board performance and employability include strengthening professional education subjects, providing practical teaching experiences, emphasizing key competencies, and implementing continuous monitoring and evaluation of program outcomes.

IMPACT AND IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

School Administrators. School administrators can leverage the high percentage of degree holders among the graduates to showcase the quality of education offered by the institution, attracting potential students and parents.

Department. The emphasis on useful competencies learned by the graduates suggests that departments should continue nurturing and enhancing these skills through relevant coursework and practical experiences to better prepare students for their future careers.

Teachers. Teachers can further emphasize the development of communication, critical thinking, problem-solving, and relational skills to empower students with essential attributes that will contribute to their success in both academic and professional settings.

REFERENCES

1. *Tertiary Education*. (n.d.). World Bank. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/tertiaryeducation>
2. Woya, A. A. (2019). Employability among Statistics Graduates: Graduates' Attributes, Competence, and Quality of Education. *Education Research International*, 2019, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/7285491>
3. Andrin, G. R., Miñoza, K. L., Salinas, J. A. (2022). Tracer study of St. Paul University Graduate School and Professional Studies for Academic Year 2015-2016. *European Scholar Journal (ESJ)*, 3(4), 130. <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/es/article/view/2144/1792>
4. Dimaculangan, S. (2015). CHED Tracer Questionnaire 1. https://www.academia.edu/16281872/CHED_Tracer_Questionnaire_1
5. Chua, L. L., Etbucan, J. O., Illut, E. B., Gulang, C. P., Mahusay, M.G. (2016). Professional Qualifications, Academic Competencies of Teachers, and Employability of Graduates in a University. *IAMURE Multidisciplinary Research*, 15, 1-28.
6. South, L., Saffo, D., Vitek, O., Dunne, C., & Borkin, M. A. (2022). Effective Use of Likert Scales in Visualization Evaluations: A Systematic Review. *Computer Graphics Forum*, 41(3), 43–55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cgf.14521>
7. Ramirez, T. L., Cruz, L. T., Alcantara N. V. (2014). Tracer Study of RTU Graduates: An Analysis. *Research World – Journal of Arts, Science and Commerce*, 5(1), 66-76. https://www.academia.edu/14727167/TRACER_STUDY_OF_RTU_GRADUATES_AN_ANALYSIS
8. Stoffberg, Y., Ferreira, N., & Twum-Darko, M. (2023). The Relevance of Educational Qualifications to Job Performance among Academic Administrators at a University. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 12(1), 70-82. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v12n1p70>
9. CHed Memorandum Order No. 75, s. 2017. (n.d.). <https://ched.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/CMO-No.-75-s.-2017.pdf>

10. Teachers as Lifelong Learners: Things You Must Know. (2022, August 26). ClassIn Blog. https://www.blog.classin.com/post/teachers-as-lifelong-learners?fbclid=IwAR0yZD0d83t-eBMIE1HlnJD_N-6BTv4rCy4VoRI1Bzxktvm9jG4kP1NOwA
11. *Traits of a Technically [Competent Teacher]*. (n.d.-b). ICTE Solutions. <https://www.ictesolutions.com.au/blog/the-11-traits-of-a-technically-competent-teacher/?fbclid=IwAR0Ysi9qwKpVbXq3-8zbEz0W5xn8NXkgl7dq9khx5tA9QhDSviHHAFfpK9Y>
12. Caingcoy, M. E., Ramirez, I. A. L., Gaylo, D. N., Adajar, M. I. W., Lacdag, E. O., Blanco, G. A. B. (2021). Employment, Employability, and Competencies of the Bachelor of Secondary Education Graduates. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science (IJRES)*, 7(3), 872-884. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1308154.pdf>

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